

EXPERIMENTAL FAILURE ANALYSIS OF COMPOSITES WITH ULTRA- HIGH MODULUS CARBON FIBER REINFORCEMENT FOR STATIC AND DYNAMIC LADING

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ABSTRACT

Constantly rising demands on the reliability of dynamically loaded lightweight structures require the use of modern composite materials which, because of their high specific stiffness and strength as well as their specific adjustable characteristic profiles, are a promising alternative to conventional building materials. In particular, fiber and textile reinforced composite materials open completely new possibilities in the field of ultra-lightweight structures as a result of ultra-high modulus (UHM) carbon fibers which exhibit an extremely high specific strength. In order to characterise the static and dynamic strength behaviour of such carbon fiber reinforced polymers, extensive fracture tests are first carried out through multi-axial loading. These experiments determined the strength directional dependency through superimposed short-term loads and served as the starting point for initial experiments on tube specimens in the ranges of tensile fatigue and oscillating compressive and torsion stresses. Based on the determined fracture stresses and loading cycles, corresponding Woehler-lines, dependent on the type of reinforcement, have been acquired and provide a reliable design basis for the definite verification of strength in lightweight structures under oscillating loads.

KEY WORDS: fracture tests, ultra-high modulus, dynamical loading, Woehler-line, failure analysis

INTRODUCTION

The development of complexly stressed composites structures – especially with ultra high modulus (UHM) reinforcement – requires reliable dimensioning concepts in order to take best advantage of the high degree of the material's lightweight potential. By applying the analytical and numerical computing methods developed so far for fibre-reinforced composites, thermo-mechanically induced stresses and strains can already be sufficiently determined. In contrast, performing a failure analysis adapted to fibre reinforced structures under static as well as dynamic loading still remains a source of considerable difficulty. One principal reason for this difficulty is that the use of “homogenisation techniques” in the sense of a “blurred” continuum is not permissible for a realistic description of the fracture behaviour of fibre-reinforced materials. Experience shows that the failure of fibre-reinforced composites initially takes place at the heterogeneous microstructure level, and it is exactly the micro-structural failure mechanism that takes on importance.

Although the micro-mechanical fracture has been extensively analysed in numerous studies and has also been realistically described using physically plausible models, only so-called generalising fracture criteria are currently applied to the configuration of heterogeneous anisotropic composites. These criteria non-permissibly assume a completely „blurred“ continuum without considering the micro-mechanic effects. The often applied generalising fracture criteria, such as the quadratic failure criteria of Sacharov and Tsai/Wu, combine fundamentally different fracture mechanisms in one approximate equation in the form of interpolation polynomials. However, this method cannot be used to simulate the actual gradual fracture realistically and there remain many uncertainties in the interpretation of the results of fracture tests.

Therefore, the objective is to improve the computed proof of strength of statically as well as dynamically loaded single-layered and multi-layered fibre reinforced structures based on micro-mechanic phenomena as viewed from a macro-mechanical engineering perspective. In this regard, the Institut für Leichtbau und Kunststofftechnik (ILK) at the Technische Universität Dresden applies novel, physically based strength criteria established by Hashin/Puck and Cuntze, that enable not only the determination of the relative material loading, but also a differentiation between the fracture modes.

For the fundamental characterisation of the static and dynamical failure behaviour of UHM-carbon fibre-reinforced composites, fracture tests under uni- and multiaxial loading have been carried out on tangentially as well as $\pm 30^\circ$ - and $\pm 45^\circ$ -wound tube specimens. The directional strength data, determined under quasi-static loading, are the basis for fatigue tests in one load step in the range of pulsating tensile stresses as well as of compressive stresses. Based on the experimental results, Woehler-lines have been developed, which serve for a realistic stress analysis of lightweight structures with UHM-fibre reinforcement under dynamic loading.

TUBE SPECIMENS AND EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAM

The tensile/compression-torsion experiment on tangentially and lattice wound standard tube specimens was used to determine the static and dynamic strengths (Fig. 1 [1, 2]). The tube wall thickness was 1.0 mm. The investigated tube specimens were produced from pitch-based carbon fiber rovings (K63712 DIALED, Mitsubishi, Japan) with the winding angles of 90° , $\pm 30^\circ$ and $\pm 45^\circ$. Epoxy resin Araldit LY564 was used for the matrix material.

Figure 1: Standard tube specimens for the tensile/compression-torsion (Z/D-T) experiments

In order to characterize the static strength behavior of UHM carbon composites, extensive quasi-static fracturing experiments were first carried out under single axis tensile, compression and torsion loading as well as multi-axial tensile/compression-torsion loading [2]. On one hand, the fracturing experiments enabled the determination of the relevant failure stresses and on the other hand, above all on the parallel wound tube specimens, made it possible to identify the corresponding fracture angle.

Short-term loads were used to determine the strength directional dependency. These experiments served as the starting point for the initial experiments on tube specimens. In the pulsating tensile stress range (load path 1) and the oscillating compressive stress range (load path 5), the stress ratios of minimum stress limit to maximum stress limit, $R = \sigma_{\min}/\sigma_{\max}$, (constant amplitude) were chosen according to Figure 2 as $R = 0.1$ and $R = 10$, respectively. The amplitude adjustments were made in such a way that the maximum and minimum stresses were 0.9 to 0.5 times that of the determined static tensile strengths σ_{ts} and compressive strengths σ_{cs} respectively.

Figure 2: Correlation of the dynamic experiments with a fracture curve in the (σ_2, τ_{21}) -stress plane

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The fatigue experiments were carried out on a PSB 100 hydrodynamic testing instrument (INSTRON, UK) which was load controlled. During the fatigue experiment, a test frequency of 3-5 Hz was chosen in order to avoid extreme heating of the test specimens which would lead to inaccurate results [4-6]. To ensure that the test specimen temperature did not exceed 30 °C, temperature was continually monitored.

The experimental results from the pulsating tensile stress and oscillating compressive stress investigations of 90°, ±30° and ±45° tube specimens with ultrahigh C-fiber reinforcement are shown as normalized Woehler-lines in Figures 3-8. These figures include trend-lines and the mean values for strength.

Figure 3: Fatigue behavior of 90° wound specimens in the range for pulsating tensile stresses

In the pulsating tensile stress range, a comparison of the normalized Woehler-lines and the corresponding trend-lines as a function of the wind angles reveals a large reduction in strength for the ±45° specimens. However, the strength degradation was significantly lower for the tangentially wound specimens.

Figure 4: Fatigue behavior of $\pm 30^\circ$ wound specimens in the range for pulsating tensile stresses

Figure 5: Fatigue behavior of $\pm 45^\circ$ wound specimens in the range for pulsating tensile stresses

A similar fatigue behavior was observed in the oscillating compressive stress range (Figures 6-8). Although lower than in the pulsating tensile stress range, the greatest reduction in strength was also found on the $\pm 45^\circ$ specimens. On the other hand, the degradation of the 90° specimens increased while the reduction in fatigue strength of the $\pm 30^\circ$ specimens remained virtually unchanged. Therefore, in comparison to the 90° and $\pm 30^\circ$ specimens, the difference in the degradation of the $\pm 45^\circ$ specimens is not as extreme as in the pulsating tensile stress range.

Figure 6: Fatigue behavior of 90° wound specimens in the range for oscillating compressive stresses

Figure 7: Fatigue behavior of ±30° wound specimens in the range for oscillating compressive stresses

Figure 8: Fatigue behavior of ±45° wound specimens in the range for oscillating compressive stresses

In addition to the strength experiments, the dependence of the failure phenomena on the type of loading was investigated. To this end, the damaged specimens were assessed with regard to their fracture images and the ensuing fracture angles.

The successive matrix failure during dynamic loading is easily recognizable in the 90° specimens under tensile stress (Fig. 9). While a smooth fracture resulted on 90° wound tubes during the static fracture experiment, under dynamic loading the produced fracture was spiral in appearance. This effect can be traced back to a pattern of micro-cracks in the matrix which were caused by a progressively increasing number of loading cycles. On the other hand, in the static experiments, the matrix material was not previously damaged through dynamically induced micro-cracks. The external loads can be transferred onto the fibers. In this case, the fracture develops as a fiber fracture – promoted by the extreme brittleness of the UHM C-fibers. This effect can be seen everywhere on a clean, flat fracture surface.

To a large extent, the fracture surfaces of the 90° specimens which failed under static as well as dynamic compression loading correspond to each other. They show different, non-zero fracture angles which is in agreement with the Hashin/Puck failure criteria [1, 5]. The test specimens which failed under tensile stress do not show this defining fracture angle, rather an angle of 0°.

Figure 9: Typical fracture images of 90° tube specimens following static and dynamic loading

Characteristic fracture images of representative $\pm 45^\circ$ specimens from the static tensile and compression tests as well as the pulsating tensile stress and oscillating compression stress experiments are shown in Figure 10. Comparable fracture images were seen for specimens with the same wind angle under the same type of loading. Thus, a clear “V shape” was observed for $\pm 45^\circ$ specimens in the tensile range. The fibers slid off of each other. The impact of dynamic and static loading revealed nearly no differences in the fracture images. Following a closer examination of the fracture surfaces, only the strongly fragmented formation of the dynamically loaded specimens is noticeable. The resulting matrix cracks, up to the point where all fibers have cracks, led to an increasing transfer of stress onto the fibers. Consequently, this led to fiber failure and the fragmenting of many components. The destroyed matrix can no longer ensure the necessary strength. The fracture surfaces resulting from the static load impact are less fissured and the matrix can, to a large extent, transfer the load.

Figure 10: Typical fracture images of $\pm 45^\circ$ tube specimens following static and dynamic loading

For the $\pm 30^\circ$ specimens, a comparable “V shape” in the fracture surfaces is only seen as a result of compressive stress. As in the abovementioned cases, the fracture images of the statically and dynamically loaded specimens are similar (Fig. 11). However, the formation of the “V” is not as well developed. Under pulsating tensile loading, the $\pm 30^\circ$ tube specimens exhibited a more circular, strongly fragmented type of failure. In these cases, the fibers failed faster, eliminating a pronounced sliding effect.

Figure 11: Typical fracture images of $\pm 30^\circ$ tube specimens following static and dynamic loading

FUTURE INVESTIGATIONS

In future investigations, quasi-static and dynamic torsion experiments as well as superimposed tensile/compression-torsion experiments on tangentially and lattice wound tube specimens will be carried out. These experiments will aid in the completion of the institute’s materials database on the fundamental strengths (tensile, compression and shear) of 90° wound specimens, including under quasi-static and dynamic loading. To a large extent, these fundamental strengths permit the verification of the physically proven failure criteria for multi-axial quasi-static loading and on the other hand, the applicability of new failure criteria in dynamic loading cases. Furthermore, an investigation is planned on the applicability of the Hashin/Puck failure criteria to lattice wound tube specimens under static and dynamic loading. If necessary, the fracturing conditions will be modified [7].

CONCLUSIONS

Due to their high specific strength and stiffness, carbon fiber reinforced polymers, especially those with ultra-high modular carbon reinforcement, are particularly suitable for use in fast-moving and accelerating building components. In addition to static loading, such building components are often subjected to oscillating stresses. The knowledge of dynamic failure behavior under oscillating loads is essential for the construction of safe building components which can withstand stress.

Initial oscillating strength experiments on carbon fiber reinforced synthetics using pulsating tensile and compression loading were carried out in order to determine the fatigue behavior. The experiments provided clarification on the questions pertaining to mechanical materials in light of the effective failure mechanisms and the ensuing series of fractures.

Based on the experimental results, the corresponding Woehler-lines, which were dependent on the type of reinforcement, were obtained. These data provides a reliable design basis for the definite verification of strength in lightweight structures made from UHM C-composites under oscillating loads.

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